

shows an increase in the value of k_1 from 25.05 to $66.46 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at $[\text{HSO}_4^-] = 0.5 \text{ M}$, and 1.5 M , respectively. A linear dependence of rate on $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ suggests its involvement in the mechanism of the reaction. The oxidation of cysteine has been studied over the temperature range $30-45^\circ$ and the activation parameters evaluated using least-square method are as follows: $E_a = 58.68 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $A = 2.1 \times 10^{-8} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S = -86.0 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

The addition of acrylonitrile effects polymerisation, suggesting that the reaction involves free radical formation and V^{V} acts as one-electron oxidant. The stoichiometry of the reaction is found to be 6 moles of V^{V} to 1 mole of cysteine. Cysteic acid is identified as the oxidation product by chromatography.

Mechanism: A number of species of V^{V} have been reported in aqueous acidic medium depending upon the concentration and nature of the acid⁶⁻⁸. In the present study, a unit dependence of rate on H^+ suggests $\text{V}(\text{OH})_2^+$ as the oxidising species of V^{V} . Further, the dependence of rate on unit concentration of HSO_4^- indicates the formation of 1:1 bisulphate- V^{V} complex as $\text{V}(\text{OH})_2 \text{HSO}_4^+$ which acts as an active oxidising species.

In cysteine the attack may occur either at the nitrogen atom or at the sulphur atom. Since sulphur is more nucleophilic than nitrogen, it may transfer electrons more easily to V^{V} which is electrophilic. This is followed by the release of protons by S-H fission from thiol group leading to the formation of intermediate complex. Later the complex suffers attack by water molecule in the rate determining step. The following mechanistic steps may be suggested,

On the above suggested steps the rate law can be derived as

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k K_2 K_3 [\text{Cyst}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{HSO}_4^-]}{1 + K_2 [\text{H}^+] [\text{HSO}_4^-] + K_2 K_3 [\text{Cyst}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{HSO}_4^-]} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{[\text{Cyst}]} \left\{ \frac{1}{k K_2 K_3 [\text{H}^+] [\text{HSO}_4^-]} + \frac{1}{k K_3} \right\} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (7)$$

A double reciprocal plot between k_{obs} and $[\text{Cysteine}]$ was obtained linear with positive intercept confirming the complex formation. Further, according to

Wells and Kuritsyn⁹, the equilibrium constant for the formation of $\text{V}(\text{OH})_2^+$ is very small and so K_2 may also be assumed to be very small and equation (6) is thus reduced to

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k K_2 K_3 [\text{Cysteine}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{HSO}_4^-] \quad (8)$$

The above proposed steps and the rate law incorporates the experimental results.

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Chloride-Inhibited Chromium(VI) Oxidation of Allyl Alcohol in 90% Aqueous Acetone

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It is well understood that in dilute acid solutions, chromium(vi) is mainly in the form of the acid chromate ion¹, HCrO_4^- . In presence of anions (A^-), this species is transformed to ACrO_4^- , the oxidising capacity being dependent on the nature of the anion¹⁻³. Thus, chlorochromate, ClCrO_4^- , formed in presence of chloride ions, is a less powerful oxidant than the acid chromate ion in aqueous acetic acid. The formation of chlorochromate is substantially enhanced as the dielectric constant of the solvent decreases. The equilibrium constant of formation of this species has been shown to be 17 in water² but is very high (1.1×10^6) in 87.5% aqueous acetic acid³. The dimerisation constant of the acid chromate ion (K_d) is also largely affected by the lowering of the dielectric constant of the medium. In this study, we have attempted to obtain the dimerisation constants of chromium(vi) in aqueous acetone media. We have also furnished details of the inhibition of the chromium(vi) oxidation of allyl alcohol by chloride ions in 90% acetone

and in aqueous solution. Although it is known that ClCrO_3^- is a less powerful oxidant than HCrO_4^- in 86.5% acetic acid, no comparison of the relative oxidising abilities has so far been made.

Experimental

The materials and kinetic methods were as reported earlier⁴. Runs in 90% acetone were carried out at 0° when very little oxidation of acetone by chromium(vi) occurred. Runs in aqueous media were at 24°. Spectra were recorded on a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 2000 instrument using matched 1 cm cells. The chromium(vi) dimerisation constants in aqueous acetone at 25° were found by the procedure of Neuss and Rieman⁵. The pH's of solutions were measured immediately after addition of acetone before any significant reaction between the chromium(vi) and acetone had occurred. The dimerisation constants (K_d) were 42, 44, 386 and 670 in 0, 20, 40 and 60% acetone solutions, respectively. In solutions of higher percentage of acetone, dissolution of solutes became difficult and K_d was not determined.

Results and Discussion

The chromium(vi) dimerisation constant increases with increasing acetone content in the medium, and hence it is likely to be present increasingly as a dimer in such media. The chromium(vi) oxidation of allyl alcohol in 90% acetone⁴ is known to involve the acid chromate ion, HCrO_4^- , as the oxidant species and this is converted into HCrO_3Cl in presence of chloride¹. In media of low polarity as 90% acetone where the dimerisation is extensive, the chlorochromate formation may occur via monomer or directly as shown in equation (1). As can be seen in Fig. 1, in an aqueous medium

or

as well as in 90% acetone, the spectrum of chromium(vi) undergoes similar changes in presence of chloride ions, as in the case of chromium(vi) in 86.5% acetic acid³. Chloride ions decrease the rate of oxidation in water and in 90% acetone which may be expected due to the oxidant being converted into chlorochromate. It is also noteworthy that in media containing high percentages of acetic acid, the rate of oxidation increases steeply which may be ascribed⁶ due to the unidentifiable species, acetochromate, $\text{CH}_3\text{COOCrO}_3^-$.

The effect of chloride on the chromium(vi) oxidation of allyl alcohol in 90% acetone and in an aqueous medium (Table 1) shows that the first order rate constant decreases appreciably in presence of increasing chloride concentration. But in

Fig. 1. (a) Spectrum of HCrO_4^- (...) and ClCrO_3^- (—) in aqueous medium; (b) spectrum of HCrO_4^- (...) and ClCrO_3^- (—) in 90% acetone medium.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CHLORIDE ON CHROMIUM(VI) OXIDATION OF ALLYL ALCOHOL

[Alc]=0.51 M, [H⁺]=0.092 M, μ=0.12 M

90% Acetone solution		Aqueous solution	
[Cr ^{VI}]=0.0017 M; Temp.=0°		[Cr ^{VI}]=0.0023 M; Temp.=24°	
[Cl ⁻] × 10 ³	Rate constant k_1 (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)	[Cl ⁻] × 10 ³	Rate constant k_1 (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)
0	3.95	0	4.66
0.5	3.01		
1.0	2.10	5.0	4.40
2.0	1.21		
2.4	0.677	10.0	4.32
2.75	0.544		
3.0	0.425		

aqueous medium, the effect of chloride is much less. These effects may be understood in terms of the extensive formation of chlorochromate in a low polar medium (aqueous acetone) as compared to the aqueous medium. The effect of chloride on the oxidation may be due to two parallel paths as shown in equation (2) involving the two oxidant species, acid chromate and chlorochromate³. This

$$-\frac{d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{dt} = k_{\text{oxpt}} [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] = k_{\text{HCrO}_4^-} [\text{HCrO}_4^-] + k_{\text{ClCrO}_3^-} [\text{ClCrO}_3^-] \quad (2)$$

analysis (Table 2) where the equilibrium constants of chlorochromate, derived from kinetic data in the three media, namely, 90% acetone, aqueous solution and 86.5% acetic acid are compared, shows that in the first and last cases, the formation of chlorochromate is facile to a remarkable extent, whereas

TABLE 2—RELATIVE OXIDISING ABILITIES OF ACID CHROMATE AND CHLOROCHROMATE

Solvent	90% Acetone (v/v)	Aqueous solution	86.5% Acetic acid
Equilibrium constant of formation ($K_{\text{ClCrO}_3^-}$)	1.4×10^6	42	1.1×10^6
Relative oxidising capacities ($k_{\text{HCrO}_4^-}/k_{\text{ClCrO}_3^-}$)	20	22	50

in the aqueous medium, it is rather low. As compared to the value of 42 obtained from kinetics for the chlorochromate formation constant in water, a value of 17 has also been found by other methods². The comparative oxidising abilities of acid chromate and chlorochromate listed in Table 2 show that acid chromate is very potent in acetic acid and weak in aqueous medium. Such enhanced oxidising ability of chromium(VI) in media of very high acetic acid content has earlier been attributed to the formation of acetochromate³, $\text{CH}_3\text{COOCrO}_3^-$, the anion here involved with chromium(VI) being the acetate ion. Thus, if the latter is the oxidant species in aqueous acetic acid, both HCrO_4^- and ClCrO_3^- are weaker oxidants than acetochromate. It is also noteworthy that in an aqueous medium, the oxidising abilities of the different chromium(VI) species become less different than in the low polar media.

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Studies on Catalytic Action of Substituted 12-Molybdophosphoric Acid

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FROM a survey of the patent literature, Ohara and Niina¹ stated that the majority of catalysts are heteropoly compounds containing both molybdenum and phosphorous as essential elements. It contains large cluster anions called Keggin units². In its fully oxidised form, a Keggin unit possesses 40 oxygen atoms which are classified into three

bonding types³, i.e. 4-oxygen atoms which are bonded to central P^{5+} (O_p), 24 to 2 Mo^{6+} (O_b), and 12 to only 1 Mo^{6+} (O_t), where the notations denote that oxygen bonded to the central phosphorous O_p , bridging oxygen O_b , and terminal oxygen O_t , respectively.

Heteropoly compounds, such as 12-molybdophosphoric acid ($\text{H}_2\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$) have been used as an acid catalysts (e.g. hydration of propene) and also as oxidation catalysts (e.g. oxidation of methacrolein to methacrylic acid)⁴. Several studies have already been reported concerning the acidity strength measurements of these heteropoly acids, but first order kinetics studies for the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate are not involved.

The purpose of the present investigation is to shed light on how the acidity of 12-molybdophosphoric acid and its catalytic activity can be varied upon partial substitution of H^+ by some alkali metal cations, like Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ , and Bi^{3+} cations for comparison.

Experimental

12-Molybdophosphoric acid (B.D.H.) was incorporated with the nitrates of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ or Bi^{3+} . An aqueous solution containing the required amounts of these cations to form the mono and the bimetal salts with the heteropoly acid was added to a solution of 12-molybdophosphoric acid with vigorous stirring and then evaporated over a water-bath for 24 h to dryness. The produced solids were calcined at 300° for 4 h in air stream.

The ir spectra (KBr) were taken using a Perkin-Elmer 599 B spectrophotometer, in the range 4 000–200 cm^{-1} .

The acidity of the samples was estimated by measuring the liberated amounts of acid produced by the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate. The reaction was carried out in a water thermostat using a 5.0% aqueous solution of ethyl acetate at 60°. The extent of hydrolysis of ethyl acetate was determined by conventional titrimetry with 0.1 N NaOH solution and phenolphthalein as an indicator to measure the concentration of acetic acid liberated in the reaction.

The catalytic activity of the heteropoly compounds were measured via the dehydration reaction of propan-2-ol, it was carried out using a conventional flow reactor. Purified air was used as a carrier gas. The exit feed was analysed chromatographically using a Pye 104 gas chromatograph with a polyethylene glycol (20%) column coated on celite.

Results and Discussion

A series of catalysts having the general formula $\text{M}_x\text{H}_{9-x}\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ (where, $\text{M} = \text{Li}^+$, Na^+ , K^+ ; $\text{X} = 1, 2$) was prepared. In addition to this series $\text{Bi}(\text{H}_2\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40})_2$ and $\text{Bi}_2(\text{H}_2\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40})_3$ were also prepared. Fig. 1 shows the ir spectra for these catalysts